

An Expression A Day

AEAD PDF Book

No. 101-200 / 100 entries

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It depends.

ばあい
場合による

Baai ni yoru.

It depends.

Variants

- 場合による
It depends.
- 場合によります
That depends.
- ケースバイケース
Case by case.

Adjusted Expression

ばあい
場合によります。

It depends on the situation.

Example

A 「いつでも、そうなりますか」 B 「いや、^{ばあい}場合による」

A: Does it always happen? B: No, it depends.

Notes

The phrase "baai ni yoru" is used to express that something changes depending on the situation. It can also be said as "baai ni yorimasu," but since it often refers to a general interpretation, it does not always need to

be expressed politely. In actual conversation, speakers switch between plain and polite forms depending on the situation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

avoiding generalization

indicating conditions

vague response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

conditional expression

response expression

That sounds tough.

それはきついですね。

Sore wa kitsui desu ne.

That sounds tough.

Variants

- それはきついですね。
That sounds tough.
- それはきついね。
That's tough.
- きついですね。
That must be tough.

Adjusted Expression

それは大変ですね。

That sounds difficult.

Example

A 「しけん試験がちか近づいていて、まいにちべんきょうづ毎日勉強漬けです」 B 「それはきついですね」

A: The exam is approaching, and I'm studying every day. B: That sounds tough.

Notes

The phrase "sore wa kitsui desu ne" is used to express that a situation sounds difficult or tough, often showing empathy for the other person. The adjective "kitsui" describes something physically or mentally

demanding. It can also be used before a noun, such as "kitsui shigoto" (a tough job) or "kitsui joukyou" (a difficult situation).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

showing empathy

evaluating a situation

showing consideration

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of empathy

No matter what.

どうしても

Doushitemo.

No matter what.

Variants

- どうしても
No matter what.
- どうしても～したい
I really want to...
- どうしても～したくて
I just have to...

Adjusted Expression

どうしても、お^あ会い^{おも}したいと思^{おも}います。

I really would like to meet you.

Example

どうしても、^{こんばん}今晩は^{きみ}君に^あ会^あいたい。

I want to see you tonight no matter what.

Notes

The phrase "doushitemo" expresses a strong determination to do something regardless of circumstances. It is an adverb similar to "no matter what" or "by all means." You may hear it often in TV dramas, but

if you actually use it in real life, the result could be either a great success or a complete failure.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

determination

emphasis

strong desire

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of emphasis

expression of strong feeling

Exhausted

くたくた

Kutakuta

Exhausted

Variants

- くたくた
Exhausted
- くたくたになる
I'm exhausted

Adjusted Expression

くたくたです

I'm exhausted.

Example

A 「今日は、^{きょう}仕事で、^{しごと}くたくた」

A: I'm exhausted today from work.

Notes

The phrase "kutakuta" is used to express that you are exhausted or very tired. It can refer to both physical and mental fatigue.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a state

sharing fatigue

colloquial expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

state expression

fatigue expression

colloquial expression

Full of energy

い い
生き生きしてる

Ikiiki shiteru

Full of energy

Variants

- 生き生きしてる

Full of energy

- 生き生きしている

Lively

- 生き生きとしている

Full of life

Adjusted Expression

生き生きしています

She is full of energy.

Example

A 「なんか、生き生きしてる」 B 「好きな仕事をしてるからかな？」

A: She looks lively. B: Maybe it's because she's doing work she loves?

Notes

The phrase "ikiiki shiteru" is used to express that someone is full of energy and lively.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

describing someone's state

positive evaluation

colloquial expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

state-description expression

positive-evaluation expression

colloquial expression

It all comes down to that

それに^っ尽きるよね

Sore ni tsukuru yo ne

It all comes down to that

Variants

- それに^っ尽きるよね
It all comes down to that
- それに^っ尽きる
That's what it all comes down to, right?
- 結局それだよ
That's really what it comes down to

Adjusted Expression

それに^っ尽きます

That is what it comes down to.

Example

A 「成功^{せいこう}するためには、準備^{じゅんび}とタイミング^{たいみんぐ}、それに^っ尽きるよね」

A: To succeed, it all comes down to preparation and timing, right?

Notes

The phrase "sore ni tsukuru yo ne" is used to express that everything can be reduced to one key point. "Tsukuru" here means that things come down to or boil down to a single factor. The ending "yo ne" adds a sense of shared understanding and invites agreement.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

summarizing a point

sharing an evaluation

seeking agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

summary expression

evaluation-sharing expression

agreement-seeking expression

Can that really happen?

そんなことある？

Sonna koto aru?

Can that really happen?

Variants

- そんなことある？
Can that really happen?
- そんなことあるの？
Does that really happen?
- マジで？
Seriously?

Adjusted Expression

そのようなことはありますか？

Is that really possible?

Example

A 「きのう、いちにちでさんかいもくるまがこしょうしたの！そんなことある？」

A: My car broke down three times in one day yesterday! Can that really happen?

Notes

The phrase "sonna koto aru?" is used to express surprise or disbelief when something unexpected happens. It can also be used to ask whether

something is actually possible. In conversation, raising your voice slightly can add a sense of surprise or disbelief.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing surprise

expressing disbelief

checking possibility

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

surprise expression

disbelief expression

checking expression

I see

ああ、そういうことか！

Aa, sou iu koto ka!

I see, that's what it is!

Variants

- ああ、そういうことか！
I see, that's what it is!
- ああ、そうか！
I see!
- なるほど！
Oh, I see.

Adjusted Expression

ああ、そういうことですか

I see.

Example

A 「エレベーターが来なくて、不思議に思って」 B 「点検中って書いてあるね」

A 「ああ、そういうことか！」

A: The elevator didn't come, and I was wondering. B: It says 'under maintenance.' A: I see, that's what it is!

Notes

The phrase "aa, sou iu koto ka!" is used to express that you have understood the other person's explanation. It is typically used after

hearing a specific explanation. Although each word in the phrase is basic, their combination shows a natural and effective use of language in conversation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing understanding

sharing realization

expressing agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

understanding expression

realization expression

agreement expression

It's about time

そろそろ

Sorosoro

It's about time

Variants

- そろそろ

It's about time

- もうそろそろ

soon

-

It should be about time

Adjusted Expression

そろそろです

It is about time.

Example

A 「電車、^こ来ないね」 B 「そろそろ^く来るよ」

A: The train isn't coming. B: It should come soon.

Notes

The phrase "sorosoro" is used to express that something is about to happen or that you are about to do something. It is often placed before a verb, as in "sorosoro kuru deshou" (it should come soon), "sorosoro

ikimashou" (it's about time to go), and "sorosoro nemashou" (it's about time to go to bed).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

indicating time is near

prompting action

expressing expectation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

time expression

action-prompting expression

expectation expression

It defeats the purpose

元も子もない

Moto mo ko mo nai

It defeats the purpose

Variants

- 元も子もない
It defeats the purpose
- それじゃ元も子もない
That would defeat the purpose
- That ruins everything

Adjusted Expression

それでは元も子もありません

That defeats the purpose.

Example

無理なダイエットをして体調を崩しては、元も子もない。

If you ruin your health with an extreme diet, it defeats the purpose.

Notes

The phrase "moto mo ko mo nai" is used to express that something loses all its value or meaning, making the effort pointless. The words "moto" (origin) and "ko" (result or outcome) together suggest losing both the basis and the result, leaving nothing of value.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

pointing out pointlessness

expressing loss of value

rejecting an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluation expression

negative evaluation expression

result evaluation expression

I can't ask someone else to do it

たの
頼むわけにはいかない

Tanomu wake ni wa ikanai

I can't ask someone else to do it

Variants

- 頼むわけにはいかない
I can't ask someone else to do it
- 頼めない
I can't ask anyone to do it

Adjusted Expression

たの
頼むわけにはいきません

I cannot ask someone else to do it.

Example

じぶん
自分のことだから、たにん他人にたの頼むわけにはいかない。

It's my own responsibility, so I can't ask someone else to do it.

Notes

The phrase "tanomu wake ni wa ikanai" is used to express that you cannot ask someone to do something. It is used when doing so would be inappropriate, such as when it is your own responsibility or problem. The pattern "~wake ni wa ikanai" does not simply mean 'impossible'; it expresses that something cannot be done due to social, moral, or situational reasons.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing constraint

taking responsibility

restraining an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

constraint expression

responsibility expression

judgment expression

I'm feeling much better

だいぶ^よ良くなりました

Daibu yoku narimashita

I'm feeling much better

Variants

- だいぶ良くなりました
I'm feeling much better
- だいぶ良くなっています
I'm doing considerably better
- だいぶ良くなった
I'm much better

Adjusted Expression

だいぶ^よ良くなっています

I'm doing considerably better.

Example

A 「風邪、大丈夫？」 B 「だいぶ^よ良くなったよ」

A: Are you okay with your cold? B: I'm much better.

Notes

The phrase "daibu yoku narimashita" is used to express that the situation has improved. The word "daibu" is an adverb that means "much" or "considerably." It is used to express that the situation has improved.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing improvement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

state expression

recovery expression

Right?

～でしょ？

~desho?

Right?

Variants

- ～でしょ？

Right?

- ～でしょう？

Isn't it?

Adjusted Expression

～でしょうか。

Would you agree?

Example

A 「これ、おいしいね」 B 「でしょ？」

A: This is delicious. B: Right?

Notes

The phrase "~desho?" is used when the listener acknowledges something the speaker has said, and the speaker then reconfirms it. It can be used among friends, but it may sound rude when used with superiors, so care is needed.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirming agreement

reconfirming what was said

colloquial expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

agreement-confirming expression

reconfirming expression

interpersonal expression

I can't do anything about it

どうにもこうにも...

Dounimo kounimo...

I can't do anything about it

Variants

- どうにもこうにもできない
I can't do anything about it
- どうにもならない
There's nothing I can do

Adjusted Expression

どうにもこうにもできません

There is nothing I can do about it.

Example

A 「この^{もんだい}問題は^{かいけつ}どうにもこうにも解決できない」

A: This problem can't be solved no matter what.

Notes

The phrase "dounimo kounimo" is used to express that you cannot do anything about a situation, even after trying various ways.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing helplessness

expressing being stuck

sharing a situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

helplessness expression

stuck expression

situation-sharing expression

There is a secret

ひけつ
秘訣がある

Hiketsu ga aru

There is a secret

Variants

- 秘訣がある
There is a secret
- コツがある
There is a trick to it

Adjusted Expression

秘訣があります

There is a key to it.

Example

A 「成功せいこうの秘訣ひけつは何なんだと思おもう？」 B 「努力どりょくと根気こんきだと思おもう」

A: What do you think is the secret to success? B: I think it's effort and patience.

Notes

The phrase "hiketsu ga aru" is used to express that there is a secret, a key, or an effective way to do something successfully. "Hiketsu" is a noun that refers to a secret to doing something, a key to success, or an important point for achieving a result.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

suggesting a method

pointing to a key to success

sharing knowledge

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

method expression

success expression

knowledge-sharing expression

secret ingredient

かく あじ
隠し味

Kakushi aji

secret ingredient

Variants

- 隠し味
secret ingredient
- hidden flavor

Adjusted Expression

かく あじ
隠し味です

It is a secret ingredient.

Example

A 「この料理の^{りょうり}隠^{かく}し味^{あじ}は、^{ちよこれーと}チョコレートですね」

A: The secret ingredient in this dish is chocolate.

Notes

The phrase "kakushi aji" refers to a hidden flavor or a secret ingredient that enhances a dish without being immediately noticeable. "Kakushi" comes from the verb "kakusu (to hide)" and functions as a modifier, while "aji" refers to taste or flavor.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

pointing out a cooking trick

sharing a surprise

sharing knowledge

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

cooking expression

technique expression

knowledge-sharing expression

Scent

かおり
香り

Kaori

Scent

Variants

- 香り
scent
- 匂い
fragrance

Adjusted Expression

香りです

It is a scent.

Example

A 「この^{はな}花の^{かおり}香りが^す好き」

A: I like the scent of this flower.

Notes

The word "kaori" is a noun that refers to the scent or fragrance of something, such as flowers, food, or perfume. It describes something that is not visible but can be perceived through smell.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing sensory perception

expressing preference

sharing an impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

sensory expression

olfactory expression

impression expression

Smell

にお
匂い

Nioi

Smell

Variants

- 匂い
smell
- におい
odor

Adjusted Expression

にお
匂いがします

There is a smell.

Example

A 「ちょっと^{へん}変な^{にお}匂いがする」

A: I smell something strange.

Notes

The word "nioi" is a noun that refers to the smell of something. Unlike "kaori," which refers to a good smell, "nioi" can be used more broadly. It is used to express something that is not visible but can be sensed by the nose.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing sensory perception

noticing something unusual

sharing an impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

sensory expression

olfactory expression

impression expression

One shot exit

いっぱつ たいじょう
一発、退場

Ippatsu taijou

One shot exit

Variants

- 一発、退場
One shot exit
- 一発退場

Adjusted Expression

たった一度の反則で即退場です
いちどはんそくそくたいじょう

It's an immediate exit with just one foul.

Example

A 「悪質な反則で、一発、退場！」
あくしつはんそくいっぱつたいじょう

A: One shot exit for a malicious foul.

Notes

The phrase "ippatsu taijou" is used to express that someone is ejected from a game or competition with a single foul.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a harsh penalty

expressing an immediate decision

sharing a sports situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

sports expression

penalty expression

immediate-decision expression

Looks good

よさそうね

Yosasou ne

Looks good

Variants

- よさそうね
Looks good
- よさそう
Seems good
- よさげだね
Looks promising

Adjusted Expression

よさそうですね

It looks good.

Example

A 「これ、どう？」 B 「よさそうね」

A: What do you think of this? B: Looks good.

Notes

The phrase "yosasou ne" is used to express that something looks good or seems good. "Yosasou" comes from the adjective "yoi" and the ending "sou," and it expresses the speaker's impression or guess based on what they see or sense.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing an impression

expressing conjecture

sharing an evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

impression expression

conjecture expression

evaluation expression

It's fresh!

しんせん
新鮮

Shinsen

Fresh

Variants

- 新鮮

Fresh

- 新鮮だ

It's fresh

- 新鮮な

fresh

Adjusted Expression

しんせん
新鮮です

It is fresh.

Example

A 「^{しんせん}新鮮な^{やさい}野菜が^た食べたい」

A: I want to eat fresh vegetables.

Notes

The word "shinsen" is a na-adjective that means freshly harvested. It can be used not only for food but also for fresh ideas, such as "fresh ideas."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing an evaluation expressing a state sharing an impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken evaluation expression state expression

impression expression

Exactly!

そのとおり！

Sono toori!

Exactly!

Variants

- そのとおり
Exactly!
- その通り
That's right!

Adjusted Expression

そのとおりです

That is correct.

Example

A 「^{こたえ}答は、ない、ということですか」 B 「そのとおり！」

A: So you mean there is no answer? B: Exactly!

Notes

The phrase "sono toori" is used to express agreement with what the other person has said. It confirms that the statement matches the speaker's understanding, rather than making an independent judgment of correctness.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing agreement

confirming what was said

responding in conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

agreement expression

response expression

conversation expression

This and that

あれこれ

Arekore

This and that

Variants

- あれこれ
this and that
- あれやこれや
various things

Adjusted Expression

いろいろなもの

various things

Example

A 「昨日、何^{きのう}食^{なに}べた？」 B 「あれこれ^た食^たべた」

A: What did you eat yesterday? B: I tried a bit of everything.

Notes

The phrase "arekore" means various things. In conversation, it lets the speaker refer to multiple things without naming them one by one. Especially in immediate interaction, it is a convenient expression for quickly conveying a mixed or miscellaneous set of things.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

referring to unspecified things

vague listing

ellipsis in conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

vague expression

listing expression

ellipsis expression

Take a deep breath

しんこきゅう
深呼吸して

Shinkokyuu shite

Take a deep breath

Variants

- 深呼吸して
Take a deep breath
- 深呼吸してみても
Just take a deep breath

Adjusted Expression

深呼吸してください

Please take a deep breath.

Example

A 「緊張きんちょうしているときは、深呼吸しんこきゅうして」

A: When you're nervous, take a deep breath.

Notes

The phrase "shinkokyuu shite" is used to tell someone to take a deep breath when they are nervous or anxious. The word "shinkokyuu" is a noun meaning "deep breath."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouraging calmness

expressing care

prompting an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

caring expression

action-prompting expression

calming expression

more or less

たしょう
多少

Tashou

More or less

Variants

- 多少
more or less
- 多少の
some
- 多少は
to some extent

Adjusted Expression

たしょう
多少あります

There is some.

Example

A 「今日は、^{きょう}雨が^{あめ}多少^{たしょう}降る^ふかもしれない」

A: There may be some rain today.

Notes

The phrase "tashou" is used to express that there is some amount or degree of something. It can be used not only for quantity but also for the degree of something such as skill or ability.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing degree

expressing quantity

speaking in a restrained way

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

degree expression

quantity expression

restrained expression

Pros and cons

さんびりょうろん
賛否両論

Sanpi ryouronn

Pros and cons

Variants

- 賛否両論
pros and cons
- mixed opinions

Adjusted Expression

さんびりょうろん
賛否両論があります

There are pros and cons.

Example

A 「^{あたら}新しい^{せいさく}政策には、^{さんびりょうろん}賛否両論があつて、^{かんたん}そう簡単には^{けつろん}結論は^い言えませんよ
ね」

A: There are pros and cons to the new policy and it's not easy to come to a conclusion.

Notes

The phrase "sanpi ryoron" expresses that there are both positive and negative opinions about something.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing opposing evaluations

expressing divided opinions

sharing a discussion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluation expression

discussion expression

contrast expression

I've done everything I can

やり^っ尽くした

Yaritsukushita

I've done everything I can

Variants

- やり^っ尽くした

I've done everything I can

- やり切った

I've done it all

Adjusted Expression

やり^っ尽くしました

I have done everything I can.

Example

A 「^{じゅんび}準備としてはやり^っ尽くした」

A: I've done everything I can to prepare.

Notes

The phrase "yaritsukushita" is used to express that you have done everything you can. "Yari" comes from the verb "yaru," and "tsukushita" is the past form of "tsukusu," which means to use up or exhaust completely.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing completion

expressing a sense of accomplishment

showing one's limit

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

completion expression

accomplishment expression

limit expression

Can't eat it all

た
食べきれない

Tabekirenai

Can't eat it all

Variants

- 食べきれない
Can't eat it all
- 食べ切れない
Can't finish eating it

Adjusted Expression

た
食べきれません

I cannot eat it all.

Example

A 「^{おい}美味しい料理が^{りょうり}多^{おお}すぎて、^た食べきれない」

A: There are too many delicious dishes and I can't eat them all.

Notes

The phrase "tabekirenai" is used to express that you cannot finish eating all of something. Potential expressions can have different meanings depending on the situation. In the case of "tabekirenai," it means something like "I'm full and can't eat any more." In cases such as "mazukute taberarenai" (I cannot eat it because it tastes bad) or

"dokubutsu ga fukumareteite taberarenai" (I cannot eat it because it contains poison), the pattern "-kirenai" cannot be used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a limit

expressing inability to finish

explaining a state

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

limit expression

inability-to-finish expression

state expression

Continuation is power

けいぞく ちから
継続は力なり

Keizoku ha chikara nari

Continuation is power

Variants

- 継続は力なり
Continuation is power
- Perseverance is strength

Adjusted Expression

けいぞく ちから
継続は力なりです

Continuing is powerful.

Example

A 「毎日、勉強していると、成績が上がるよね」 B 「継続は力なり」

A: If you study every day, your grades will improve. B: Continuation is power.

Notes

The phrase "keizoku ha chikara nari" is a proverb expressing that continuing something leads to strength or success. "Keizoku" means continuation, and "chikara" means power or strength.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a moral presenting a value encouragement

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken proverb expression value expression

encouragement expression

In a nutshell

よう
要するに...

Yousuruni...

In a nutshell,...

Variants

- 要するに...
In a nutshell,...
- 要するに
To put it simply,...

Adjusted Expression

よう
要するに、そういうことです。

In short, that is the point.

Example

A 「^{よう}要するに、この^{きかい}機械は^{だれ}誰にでも^{つか}使えるということです」

A: In a nutshell, this machine can be used by anyone.

Notes

The phrase "yousuruni" is used to express that something is being summarized or that the main point is being explained briefly.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a summary

presenting the main point

organizing an explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

summary expression

explanation expression

organizing expression

move your hands

て うご
手を動かす

Te wo ugokasu

move your hands

Variants

- 手を動かす
move your hands
- 手を動かしてみる
try doing it with your hands

Adjusted Expression

じっさい て うご
実際に手を動かしてください

Please try doing it yourself.

Example

A 「^{かんが}考えるだけでなく、^{じっさい}実際に^て手を^{うご}動かしてみると、よくわかるよ」

A: If you don't just think about it but actually try doing it with your hands, you'll understand it better.

Notes

The phrase "te wo ugokasu" is used to express that you should actually use your hands in order to understand something. The word "te" is a noun that means "hand." The word "ugokasu" is a verb that means "to move."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouraging practice

promoting understanding

prompting action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

practice expression

understanding-promoting expression

action-prompting expression

I hope ...

～でありますように

~de arimasu you ni

I hope ...

Variants

- ～でありますように
I hope ...
- ～でありますように。
May ...

Adjusted Expression

～であることを願ねがいます

I hope that ...

Example

A 「世よの中なか、平和へいわでありますように」 B 「僕ぼくは、試験しけん、合格ごうかくできますように」

A: I hope there will be peace in the world. B: I hope I can pass the exam.

Notes

The phrase "~de arimasu you ni" is used to express a wish or hope. This expression is used in patterns such as "(verb) you ni" and "(noun + de arimasu) you ni."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a wish

expressing hope

expressing a prayer

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

wish expression

hope expression

prayer expression

A driver's license

うんてんめんきょ
運転免許

Unten menkyo

Driver's license

Variants

- 運転免許
driver's license
- 運転免許を取る
get a driver's license

Adjusted Expression

うんてんめんきょ と
運転免許を取りました。

I got my driver's license.

Example

A 「うんてんめんきょ と運転免許を取った」

A: I got my driver's license.

Notes

The phrase "unten menkyo" is a compound noun composed of two nouns: "unten" (driving) and "menkyo" (license).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

mentioning a qualification

expressing obtaining it

everyday vocabulary

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

compound noun

qualification

everyday vocabulary

Made it in time

ま あ
間に合った

Ma ni atta

Made it in time

Variants

- 間に合った
made it in time
- 間に合いました
made it just in time
- ぎりぎり間に合った
barely made it in time

Adjusted Expression

ま あ
間に合いました

I made it in time

Example

ひとつ前の電車まえ でんしゃに間に合ったま あので、予定より早くよてい はや着きましたつ。

I made it to the earlier train, so I arrived earlier than planned.

Notes

"Ma ni atta" expresses that you managed to make it in time. "Ma" means "time" or "interval," and "ni" is a particle indicating the target time or goal. "Au" is a verb meaning "to match," "to fit," or "to be in time." In real

life, there are probably more situations where you don't make it in time than when you do.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reporting that something was in time

sharing relief

immediate reaction about timing

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

time expression

reporting a result

relief

A habit

しゅうかん
習慣

Shuukan

A habit

Variants

- 習慣
a habit
- 習慣になる
become a habit
- 新しい習慣
a new habit

Adjusted Expression

あたら しゅうかん
新しい習慣ができました

I've made a new habit

Example

A 「毎日、ジョギングすることが習慣になった」

A: I've made it a habit to jog every day.

Notes

The phrase "atarashii shuukan" is used to express that you have started a new habit. "Atarashii" is an i-adjective meaning "new," and "shuukan" is a

noun meaning "habit." For example, sleeping early and waking up early for one's health, eating a little yogurt every day, etc.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

describing a habit

reporting a change of state

mentioning everyday behavior

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

state change

everyday vocabulary

Of course

もちろん

Mochiron

Of course

Variants

- もちろん
of course
- もちろんです
of course it is
- もちろんだよ
of course

Adjusted Expression

もちろんいいですよ。

Of course, that's fine.

Example

A 「^{あした}明日、^あ会える？」 B 「もちろん」

A: Can we meet tomorrow? B: Of course.

Notes

The phrase "mochiron" is used to express that something is natural or obvious.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing obviousness

giving an affirmative response

an immediate response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

affirmation

obviousness

By the way

ところで

Tokorode

By the way

Variants

- ところで
by the way
- ところでさ
by the way,
- ところでね
anyway, by the way

Adjusted Expression

ちょっと、^{わだい}話題^かは変わるんですが、...

Well, this is a bit of a change of topic, but ...

Example

A 「^{きのう}昨日、^{えいが}映画^みを見たよ」 B 「^{あした}そうなんだ。ところで、^{よてい}明日の予定は？」 A
「^{とく}特^にはないよ」

A: I watched a movie yesterday. B: I see. By the way, what are your plans for tomorrow? A: Nothing special.

Notes

The phrase "tokorode" is used to change the subject of the conversation or to ask a question.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

changing the topic

introducing a question

shifting the flow of conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

discourse marker

topic shift

conversation management

About ...

～について

~Ni tsuite

About ...

Variants

- ～について
about ...
- ～につきまして
concerning ...
- ～については
regarding ...

Adjusted Expression

～についてですが、 ...

About ..., but ...

Example

A 「書類しよるいの書き方か かたについておし教えていただけませんか」

A: Could you tell me how to write the document?

Notes

The phrase "ni tsuite" is used to ask for information or instructions about something.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a topic

indicating the target of explanation

asking for information

Tags EN

immediate grammar

particle expression

topic presentation

explanation

question

Suddenly

とつぜん
突然

Totsuzen

Suddenly

Variants

- 突然
suddenly
- 突然に
all of a sudden
- 突然ですが
suddenly, but ...

Adjusted Expression

とつぜん
突然ではありますが、...

Suddenly, but ...

Example

A 「突然、電話が鳴って、びっくりした」

A: Suddenly, the phone rang and I was surprised.

Notes

The word "totsuzen" is an adverb that means "suddenly" or "unexpectedly."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing suddenness

sharing surprise

introducing an unexpected turn

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

colloquial

surprise

unexpected event

Let's keep going

どんどん^{すす}進めよう

Dondon susumeyou

Let's keep going

Variants

- どんどん進めよう
let's keep going
- どんどん進めていこう
let's keep moving forward
- さあ、どんどん進めよう
come on, let's keep going

Adjusted Expression

さあ、どんどん^{すす}進めましょう

Come on, let's keep going

Example

A 「このプロジェクトの^{ぶろじえくと}条件^{じょうけん}は、すべて揃^{そろ}った。さあ、どんどん^{すす}進めよう」

A: All the conditions for this project are in place. Let's keep going.

Notes

The phrase "dondon susumeyou" is used to express that you should continue to move forward without stopping. The word "dondon" is an adverb that means "more and more" or "steadily." The word

"susumeyou" is the volitional form of the verb "susumeru," which means "to advance" or "to proceed."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouraging progress

urging continuation of work

adding momentum

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

invitation

progress

momentum

Please help yourself.

じゅう
ご自由に

Go jiyuu ni

Please help yourself.

Variants

- ご自由に
please help yourself
- ご自由にどうぞ
please feel free
- ご自由にお取りください
please take one freely

Adjusted Expression

じゅうと
ご自由にお取りください

Please take one freely

Example

A 「パンフレット、ひとつ、よろしいですか？」 B 「ええ、どうぞ、ご自由にお取りください」

A: Can I have a pamphlet? B: Yes, please help yourself.

Notes

"Jiyuu" means "freedom" or "liberty." The construction "go...ni" makes "jiyuu" more polite. Similarly, "o...kudasai" adds politeness to the verb

"tori," which comes from "toru" ("to take"). "Toru" is first changed to "torimasu," and then "masu" is removed to form "tori." The phrase "go jiyuu ni otori kudasai" is a polite way to say that you can take something freely or at your own discretion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

politely giving permission

showing consideration to the other person

guiding expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

honorific expression

polite expression

guiding expression

permission expression

service situation

A coincidence

ぐうぜん いっち
偶然の一致

Guuzen no icchi

A coincidence

Variants

- 偶然の一致
a coincidence
- 単なる偶然
just a coincidence
- たまたま
by chance

Adjusted Expression

単なる^{ぐうぜん}偶然^{いっち}の一致ですよ。

It's just a coincidence

Example

A 「^{なん}何^{おな}で^{ふくて}同じ服着るの」 B 「単なる^{ぐうぜん}偶然^{いっち}の一致」

A: Why are you wearing the same clothes? B: It's just a coincidence.

Notes

The phrase "guuzen no icchi" is used to express that something is a mere coincidence. The word "guuzen" is a noun that means "chance" or

"accident." The word "icchi" is a noun that means "coincidence" or "agreement."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explaining something as coincidence

denying intentional matching

giving a light explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun phrase

explanatory expression

coincidence

colloquial

A beckoning cat

まね ねこ
招き猫

Manekineko

A beckoning cat

Variants

- 招き猫
a beckoning cat
- 招き猫が置かれている
a beckoning cat is placed there
- 招き猫を置く
place a beckoning cat

Adjusted Expression

みせ いりぐち しょうばいはんじょう ねが まね ねこ お
店の入口には、商売繁盛を願って招き猫が置かれています。

A beckoning cat is placed at the entrance of the store to wish for prosperity in business.

Example

A 「店の入口には、商売繁盛を願って招き猫が置かれている」

A: A beckoning cat is placed at the entrance of the store to wish for prosperity in business.

Notes

The phrase "manekineko" refers to a beckoning cat placed at the entrance of a store to wish for prosperity in business. The word "manekineko" is a compound noun composed of the verb "maneku" ("to beckon") and the noun "neko" ("cat").

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

describing an object

mentioning a lucky charm

describing a storefront scene

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

compound noun

cultural vocabulary

lucky charm

storefront expression

A guardian dog

こまいぬ
狛犬

Komainu

A guardian dog

Variants

- 狛犬
a guardian dog
- 狛犬が置かれている
a guardian dog is placed there
- 狛犬を見る
see a guardian dog

Adjusted Expression

じんじゃ いりぐち こまいぬ お
神社の入口に狛犬が置かれています。

A guardian dog is placed at the entrance of the shrine.

Example

A 「じんじゃ いりぐち こまいぬ お神社の入口に狛犬が置かれている」

A: A guardian dog is placed at the entrance of the shrine.

Notes

The word "komainu" refers to a guardian dog placed at the entrance of a shrine. The word "komainu" is treated here as a noun referring to that statue or figure.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

describing an object

describing a shrine scene

mentioning a cultural object

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

cultural vocabulary

shrine

ornament

I could use all the help I can get

ねこ て か
猫の手も借りたい

Neko no te mo karitai

I could use all the help I can get

Variants

- 猫の手も借りたい

I could use all the help I can get

- 猫の手も借りたいほど

I'm so busy I could even borrow a cat's paws

- 猫の手も借りたいくらい

I need all the help I can get

Adjusted Expression

いそが ねこ て か
忙しくて、猫の手も借りたいほどです。

I'm so busy that I could even borrow a cat's paws.

Example

A 「なに何かこま細かいさぎょう作業をてつだ手伝ってくれるひと人がほ欲しい」 B 「ねこ猫の手もて借りかたいね」

A: I want someone to help me with some small tasks. B: I could use all the help I can get.

Notes

The phrase "neko no te mo karitai" is used to express that you are extremely busy and want as much help as possible. It is a hyperbolic

expression: even the paws of a cat, which would not normally be very helpful, would be welcome.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

exaggerating how busy one is

expressing a lack of helping hands

sharing the feeling of wanting help

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

busyness

hyperbolic expression

lack of help

Goof off

あぶら う
油を売る

Abura wo uru

Goof off

Variants

- 油を売る
goof off
- 油を売っている
be goofing off
- 油を売っていました
was goofing off

Adjusted Expression

かれ しご ぎょうむ おこた
彼は、私語にふけり、業務を怠っています。

He is absorbed in private chatting and neglecting his duties.

Example

A 「かれ おんな こ あぶら う
彼は、女の子とおしゃべりばかりして、油を売っていました」

A: He was just chatting with girls and goofing off.

Notes

The phrase "abura wo uru" means not to sell oil literally, but to goof off without working. The word "abura" is a noun that means "oil." The word

"uru" is a verb that means "to sell." If his job was really selling oil, it would be difficult to tell whether he was working or goofing off.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that someone is slacking off

pointing out that someone is not working

light criticism or joking

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

slacking off

work situation

light criticism

Secret weapon

奥の手

Oku no te

Secret weapon

Variants

- 奥の手
secret weapon
- 奥の手を使う
use a secret weapon
- 最後の切り札
last resort

Adjusted Expression

かれ かれ、ひさく ひさくもち もち、もんだい もんだいかいけつ かいけつした。

He solved the problem by using a hidden strategy.

Example

A 「おく おくて てつか つかから、まだ大丈夫 だいじょうぶ」

A: I'll use my secret weapon, so I'm still okay.

Notes

The phrase "oku no te" is used to express that you have something hidden and use it when needed. The word "oku" means "deep" or "secret." The word "te" means "hand," and also extends to the meaning of "means" or "method."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a hidden method

announcing the use of a trump card

expressing a way to turn the situation around

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

noun phrase

strategy

trump card

Get fired

くび
首になる

Kubi ni naru

Get fired

Variants

- 首になる
get fired
- クビになる
be fired
- 首にされる
be let go

Adjusted Expression

かれ かいしゃ かいこ
彼は、会社から解雇された。

He was dismissed from the company.

Example

A 「何回も遅刻して、アルバイトを首になった」

A: I was fired from my part-time job because I was late many times.

Notes

The phrase "kubi ni naru" is used to express that you are fired from your job. The word "kubi" is a noun that means "neck." The word "naru" is a verb that means "to become."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing being fired

reporting a result

consequence of failure or carelessness

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

work situation

dismissal

Have an eye

めも
目を持っている

Me wo motteiru

Have an eye

Variants

- 目を持っている
have an eye
- 見る目がある
have an eye for
- 目が利く
have a good eye

Adjusted Expression

かれ かいが てきせつ ひょうか のうりよく も
彼は、絵画を適切に評価する能力を持っている。

He has the ability to evaluate paintings appropriately.

Example

A 「かれ かいが え み め も
彼は、絵を見る目を持っている」

A: He has an eye for pictures.

Notes

The phrase "me wo motteiru (he has the eyes to appreciate paintings)" means that he possesses the ability or sensitivity to understand and evaluate the beauty and value of paintings. It implies that he not only has

the physical ability to see but also has the aesthetic sense and understanding required to appreciate art. The word "me" is a noun that means "eye." The word "motteiru" is the te-form of the verb "motsu" that means "to have."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluating ability or sensitivity

expressing discernment

evaluating a person

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

ability evaluation

sensitivity

I don't wanna hear that.

みみ いた
耳が痛い

Mimi ga itai

I don't wanna hear that.

Variants

- 耳が痛い
I don't wanna hear that
- 耳が痛い話
that hits too close to home
- 耳の中が痛い
my ear hurts

Adjusted Expression

(それは、^{じぶん}自分に(とって)都合の悪い^{わる}指摘^{してき}だ。

That is a point that is inconvenient for me.

Example

A 「それは、^{みみ}耳^{いた}が^{はなし}痛い話だ」

A: That's a painful story.

Notes

There are some cases where the phrase "mimi ga itai" is used to express that your ear hurts, but in that case, you say "mimi no naka ga itai (my ear hurts)." Generally, the expression "mimi ga itai" is used when you

listen to someone's story and feel uncomfortable because the content is inconvenient for you.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reacting to an inconvenient truth

expressing self-awareness lightly

sharing discomfort

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

self-awareness

discomfort

Go to great lengths

ほね お
骨を折る

Hone wo oru

Go to great lengths

Variants

- 骨を折る
go to great lengths
- 骨を折ってくれる
make great efforts
- 骨を折った
put in a lot of effort

Adjusted Expression

せんせい とつきよしゆとく どりよく
先生は、特許取得のために、さまざまな努力をしてくださいました。

The teacher made various efforts to obtain the patent.

Example

A 「せんせい とつきよしゆとく ほね お
先生は、特許取得のために、いろいろ骨を折ってくださいました」

A: The teacher went to great lengths to obtain a patent.

Notes

The phrase "hone wo oru" is used to express that you put a lot of effort into something. It does not mean that you actually broke a bone. The

word "hone" is a noun that means "bone." The word "oru" is a verb that means "to break."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing effort

showing gratitude for someone's efforts

mentioning trouble taken

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

effort

dedication

expression of gratitude

Be malicious

はら くろ
腹が黒い

Hara ga kuroi

Be malicious

Variants

- 腹が黒い
be malicious
- 腹黒い
be scheming
- 腹が黒そうだ
be sinister

Adjusted Expression

かれ あくい も
彼は、悪意を持っている。

He has malicious intent.

Example

A 「かれは、腹が黒い」

A: He is malicious.

Notes

The phrase "hara ga kuroi" is used to express that someone has malice. It does not mean that the person's internal organs are actually black. The

word "hara" is a noun that means "stomach." The word "kuroi" is an i-adjective that means "black."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluating someone as malicious

giving a negative character evaluation

describing someone as having hidden motives

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

character evaluation

malice

personality description

Eyes pop out

め と で
目が飛び出る

Me ga tobidiru

Eyes pop out

Variants

- 目が飛び出る
eyes pop out
- 目が飛び出るほど
so surprised your eyes pop out
- 目が飛び出るほど驚く
be extremely surprised

Adjusted Expression

その値段を見て、非常に驚いた。

I was very surprised when I saw the price.

Example

A 「その値段を見て、目が飛び出た」

A: Seeing the price, my eyes popped out.

Notes

This Japanese expression means that the price was so astonishingly high that it caused an extreme reaction. The phrase "目が飛び出るほど" (me ga tobi deru hodo) literally translates to "eyes popping out," which is a vivid

way of describing someone being extremely surprised or shocked. The expression conveys that the reaction to seeing the price was intense and exaggerated, similar to how one might react if they were extremely astonished.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing strong surprise

a hyperbolic reaction to something like a price

sharing shock

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

surprise

hyperbolic expression

body expression

Have a soft spot for

め
目がない

Me ga nai

Have a soft spot for

Variants

- 目がない
have a soft spot for
- ～に目がない
can't resist
- 甘いものに目がない
have a weakness for

Adjusted Expression

かれ かれ あま あま ひじょう ひじょう す す
彼は、甘いものが非常に好きだ。

He likes sweets very much.

Example

かれ かれ あま あま め め
彼は、甘いものに目がない。

He has a sweet tooth.

Notes

The phrase "me ga nai" means that someone likes something very much. The word "me" is a noun that means "eye." The word "nai" is an i-adjective that means "not have."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing strong liking

emphasizing preference

describing a personal trait

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

preference

characterization

An egg

たまご
卵

Tamago

An egg/A talented or promising individual

Variants

- 卵
an egg
- ~の卵
a beginner with potential
- プログラマの卵
an aspiring programmer

Adjusted Expression

きみ みけいけん じゅうぶん そしつ
君はまだ未経験だが、十分な素質がある。

You are still inexperienced, but you have enough potential.

Example

きみ ぷろぐらま たまご そしつ じゅうぶん
君はまだプログラマの卵だが、素質は十分ある。

You're still an aspiring programmer, but you've got a lot of potential.

Notes

The word "tamago" is a noun that means "egg." In this expression, the word "tamago" is used metaphorically to refer to someone who is still inexperienced or a beginner in a particular field, but has the potential to

grow and develop their skills. The phrase "... no tamago" is often used to describe someone who is new to a profession or activity, but has the potential to become skilled or successful in the future.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing someone who is still inexperienced but promising

metaphorical evaluation of a person

mentioning future potential

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

metaphorical expression

character evaluation

potential

More than anything

なにより

Nani yori

More than anything

Variants

- なにより
more than anything
- 何より
above all
- 何よりの～
the best thing of all

Adjusted Expression

このプロジェクトが成功したことが、最も重要な成果です。

The success of this project is the most important achievement.

Example

このプロジェクトが成功したことがなよりの成果です。

The success of this project is the most important achievement.

Notes

The phrase "nani yori" is used to express that something is more important than anything else. The word "nani" is a pronoun that means "what." The word "yori" is a particle that is used to indicate comparison or preference.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasizing what is most important

highlighting the focus of evaluation

expressing satisfaction or relief

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverbial expression

evaluative expression

emphasis

colloquial

Atmosphere

ふんいき
雰囲気

Fun'iki

Atmosphere

Variants

- 雰囲気
atmosphere
- 雰囲気がいい
have a good atmosphere
- この店の雰囲気が好き
I like the atmosphere of this place

Adjusted Expression

わたし、この店の^{みせ}全体的な^{ぜんたいてき}感じ^{かん}が好き^すだ。

I like the overall feel of this store.

Example

A 「この店の^{みせ}雰囲気^{ふんいき}が好き^す」

A: I like the atmosphere of this store.

Notes

The word "fun'iki" is a noun that means the overall feel or atmosphere of a place or situation. When you cannot quite put your finger on what makes a place feel a certain way, using the word "fun'iki" can be helpful.

Another way to express this idea is to say "nantonaku," which means "somehow" or "in some way."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing the feel of a place or situation

giving a positive evaluation

sharing an impression that is hard to describe in words

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

evaluative expression

impression

description of place

Nostalgic

なつ
懐かしい

Natsukashii

Nostalgic

Variants

- 懐かしい
nostalgic
- 懐かしいね
that's nostalgic
- なんだか懐かしい
that feels nostalgic

Adjusted Expression

それは、^か ^こ ^{おも} ^だ 過去を思い出させる。

It reminds me of the past.

Example

A 「この^{きょく} ^き 曲を聞くと、昔^{むかし}の^{おも} ^だ ことを思い出^だす」 B 「懐^{なつ}かしいね」

Notes

The phrase "natsukashii" is used to express that something reminds you of the past and makes you feel nostalgic.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reacting to something that recalls the past

reacting to a shared memory

sharing a feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

memory

past

Delivery service

でりばりーさーびす
デリバリーサービス

Deribarii saabisu

Delivery service

Variants

- デリバリーサービス
delivery service
- デリバリーサービスを利用する
use a delivery service
- デリバリーを頼む
order delivery

Adjusted Expression

はいたつ 配達サービスりようを利用すると、いえ家にいながらたべもの食べ物をちゅうもん注文できる。

If you use a delivery service, you can order food while staying at home.

Example

A 「でりばりーさーびすデリバリーサービスりようを利用すると、いえ家にいながらたべもの食べ物をちゅうもん注文できる」

A: If you use a delivery service, you can order food while staying at home.

Notes

The phrase "deribarii saabisu" is used to express a service that delivers food or goods to your home. The word "deribarii" is a loanword from

English that means "delivery." The word "saabisu" is a loanword from English that means "service."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

describing a service

mentioning an everyday action

expressing convenience

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

loanword

everyday vocabulary

service

food

Can't wait

ま
待ちきれない

Machikirenai

Can't wait

Variants

- 待ちきれない
can't wait
- もう待ちきれない
I can't wait
- 楽しみに待ちきれない
I can't wait for it

Adjusted Expression

あした りょこう たの
明日の旅行を、とても楽しみにしている。

I am very much looking forward to tomorrow's trip.

Example

A 「あした りょこう たの 明日の旅行、楽しみだね」 B 「うん、ま 待ちきれない」

A: I'm looking forward to the trip tomorrow. B: Yeah, I can't wait.

Notes

The phrase "machikirenai" is used to express that you are looking forward to something and cannot wait for it to happen. The word "machi" is a masu-form of a verb "matsu (to wait)" such as "machi-masu."

The word "kirenai" is a negative form of the verb "kiru" that means "to be able to endure."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing strong anticipation

sharing excitement

expressing that one cannot wait

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

anticipation

excitement

Be into it

は ま
ハマる

Hamaru

Be into it

Variants

- ハマる
be into it
- はまっている
be hooked on it
- 読書にはまっている
be really into reading

Adjusted Expression

さいきん どくしょ つよ きょうみ も
最近、読書に強い興味を持っている。

Recently, I have developed a strong interest in reading.

Example

A 「最近、読書にはまっている」

A: I've been into reading books lately.

Notes

The phrase "hamaru" is used to express that you are interested in something and have been spending a lot of time on it. The word "hamaru" is a verb that means "to be into" or "to be interested in."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing strong interest

expressing being absorbed in something

sharing a recent interest

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

interest

absorption

Be concerned

き
気になる

Ki ni naru

Be concerned

Variants

- 気になる
be concerned
- 気になっている
be curious about
- 気になって眠れない
can't stop thinking about it

Adjusted Expression

(その)ドラマの続きがどうなるのか、心配で眠れない。

I can't sleep because I am worried about what will happen next in the drama.

Example

A 「そのドラマの続きがどうなるのか、気になって眠れない」

A: I can't sleep because I'm concerned about how the drama will end.

Notes

The phrase "ki ni naru" is used to express that you are concerned or interested in something. The word "ki" is a noun that means "mind" or

"spirit." The word "ni" is a particle that is used to indicate the target of an action or the direction of a movement. The word "naru" is a verb that means "to become."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing concern

expressing interest

sharing worry or curiosity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

interest

worry

A drop in the bucket

すずめ なみだ
雀の涙

Suzume no namida

A drop in the bucket

Variants

- 雀の涙
a drop in the bucket
- 雀の涙ほど
next to nothing
- ほんの雀の涙
only a tiny amount

Adjusted Expression

しょにんきゅう ひじょう すく
初任給は、非常に少ない。

My first paycheck is very small.

Example

A 「ねえ、初任給、出た？」 B 「うん、雀の涙ほどね」

A: Hey, did you get your first paycheck? B: Yeah, it's just a drop in the bucket.

Notes

The phrase "suzume no namida" is used to express that something is very small or insignificant. The word "suzume" is a noun that means "sparrow." The word "namida" is a noun that means "tear."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing small quantity

complaining about how little money or reward there is

using hyperbole for evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

quantity expression

smallness

money expression

Be stubborn

あたま かた
頭が固い

Atama ga katai

Be stubborn

Variants

- 頭が固い
be stubborn
- 頭が固いね
be inflexible
- 考え方が固い
be rigid in one's thinking

Adjusted Expression

かれ じゅうなん かんが
彼は、柔軟に考えることができない。

He is unable to think flexibly.

Example

A 「かれ じぶん いけん ま
彼は、自分の意見を曲げない」 B 「あたま かた
頭が固いね」

A: He doesn't change his opinion. B: He's stubborn.

Notes

The phrase "atama ga katai" is used to express that someone is stubborn or inflexible. The word "atama" is a noun that means "head." The word "katai" is an i-adjective that means "hard" or "stiff."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluating stubbornness pointing out inflexibility evaluating a person

Tags EN

immediate grammar idiomatic expression colloquial character evaluation

stubbornness personality description

Cut ties

て き
手を切る

Te wo kiru

Cut ties

Variants

- 手を切る
cut ties
- 手を切って
break off relations
- 関係を絶つ
end the relationship

Adjusted Expression

(この)会社かいしゃとの関係かんけいを絶ちた、もう取り引きとひは行わないおこない。

I will end our relationship with this company and will not do business with them anymore.

Example

A 「この会社かいしゃとは手を切てって、もう取り引きとひは行おこなわない」

A: I'm going to cut ties with this company and never deal with them again.

Notes

The phrase "te wo kiru" is used to express that you are going to end a relationship or connection with someone or something. The word "te" is a noun that means "hand." The word "kiru" is a verb that means "to cut."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a severed relationship

ending a business or personal connection

declaring a firm break

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

relationship

break

business dealing

Have a hard time dealing with

て や
手を焼く

Te wo yaku

Have a hard time dealing with

Variants

- 手を焼く
have a hard time dealing with
- 手を焼いている
have trouble handling
- 扱いに手を焼く
be at a loss over how to deal with

Adjusted Expression

こども たいど たいおう こま
子供の態度への対応に困っている。

I am having difficulty dealing with my child's attitude.

Example

A 「子供の態度に手を焼いている」

A: I'm having a hard time dealing with my child's attitude.

Notes

The phrase "te wo yaku" is used to express that you are having a hard time dealing with someone or something. The word "te" is a noun that means "hand." The word "yaku" is a verb that means "to bake."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing difficulty in dealing with someone or something

expressing being troubled by someone

sharing frustration or perplexity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

perplexity

interpersonal relations

children

Attract attention

ひとめ ひ
人目を引く

Hitome wo hiku

Attract attention

Variants

- 人目を引く
attract attention
- 人目を引きますね
catch people's attention
- よく人目を引く
be eye-catching

Adjusted Expression

(この)ポスターは、^{おお}多くの^{ひと}人の^{ちゅうい}注意を^ひ引く。

This poster attracts a lot of people's attention.

Example

A 「この^{ほすたー}ポスターは、^{ひとめ}人目を^ひ引きますね」

A: This poster attracts attention.

Notes

The phrase "hitome wo hiku" is used to express that something attracts attention. The word "hitome" is a noun that means "eye" or "attention." The word "hiku" is a verb that means "to pull" or "to attract."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that something draws attention

evaluating appearance or design

expressing strong visual impact

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

evaluative expression

attention

visual impression

Show up

かお だ
顔を出す

Kao wo dasu

Show up

Variants

- 顔を出す
show up
- 顔を出していない
drop by
- ちょっと顔を出す
make an appearance

Adjusted Expression

かれ さいきん きっさてん き
彼は、最近、この喫茶店に来ていない。

He has not come to this cafe recently.

Example

A 「かれ さいきん きっさてん かお だ
彼は、最近、この喫茶店に顔を出していない」

A: He hasn't shown up at this cafe recently.

Notes

The phrase "kao wo dasu" is used to express that someone appears or shows up at a place. The word "kao" is a noun that means "face." The word "dasu" is a verb that means "to put out" or "to show."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that someone appears at a place

expressing dropping by

mentioning someone's recent behavior

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

action expression

appearance

dropping by

Be considerate of

き つか
気を使う

Ki wo tsukau

Be considerate of

Variants

- 気を使う
be considerate of
- 他人に気を使う
be attentive to others
- 気を使いすぎる
be too considerate

Adjusted Expression

かのじょ たにん たい はいりょ
彼女は、他人に対して配慮をする。

She shows consideration for others.

Example

A 「かのじょ たにん き つか
「彼女は、他人に気を使う」

A: She is always considerate of others.

Notes

The phrase "ki wo tsukau" is used to express that you are considerate of others. The word "ki" is a noun that means "spirit" or "mind." The word "tsukau" is a verb that means "to use."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing consideration for others

evaluating interpersonal behavior

describing attentiveness

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

interpersonal relations

consideration

attentiveness

Tidy up

かたづ
片付ける

Katadukeru

Tidy up

Variants

- 片付ける
tidy up
- 一つ一つ片付ける
deal with one thing at a time
- 問題を片付ける
take care of a problem

Adjusted Expression

ひと ひと じゅんばん しょり
一つ一つ、順番に処理していこう。

Let's deal with them one by one in order.

Example

A 「一つ一つを片付けていこう」

A: Let's deal with them one by one.

Notes

The phrase "katadukeru" is used to express that you are tidying up or organizing things. However, "katadukeru" not only means organizing things but also means solving problems or finishing things.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing tidying up

expressing handling things one by one

expressing solving or finishing something

Tags EN

immediate grammar

verb

colloquial

tidying

handling

problem solving

Last hope

たの つな
頼みの綱

Tanomi no tsuna

Last hope

Variants

- 頼みの綱
last hope
- 最後の頼みの綱
one's last hope
- 唯一の頼みの綱
only hope

Adjusted Expression

それが、問題^{もんだい}を解決^{かいけつ}するための最後^{さいご}の手段^{しゅだん}だ。

That is the last means to solve the problem.

Example

A 「頼^{たの}み^{つな}の綱だ」

A: It's our last hope.

Notes

The phrase "tanomi no tsuna" is used to express that something is the last hope or the only way to solve a problem. The word "tanomi" is a noun

that means "request" or "hope." The word "tsuna" is a noun that means "rope."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing the last hope

expressing the only means left

expressing urgent expectation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

noun phrase

hope

problem solving

urgency

Put effort into

ちから い
力を入れる

Chikara wo ireru

Put effort into

Variants

- 力を入れる
put effort into
- 売り込みに力を入れる
focus on promoting
- 特に力を入れている
put particular effort into

Adjusted Expression

どうてん しゅりょくしょうひん はんばいそくしん じゅうてんてき と く
当店は、主力商品の販売促進に重点的に取り組んでいる。

Our store is focusing on promoting its main products.

Example

A 「当店の主力商品の売り込みに力を入れている」

A: We are putting effort into promoting our main products.

Notes

The phrase "chikara wo ireru" is used to express that you are putting effort into something. The word "chikara" is a noun that means "power" or "strength." The word "ireru" is a verb that means "to put in." Shuryoku

shouhin is a noun that means "main product." Urikomi is a noun that means "promotion."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing focused effort

expressing putting effort into something

explaining a business policy

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

effort

focus

work situation

Before I knew it

いつのまにか

Itsunomanika

Before I knew it

Variants

- いつのまにか
before I knew it
- いつの間にか
without realizing it
- いつのまにか～ていた
without noticing

Adjusted Expression

^き気づかないうちに、^{ゆうがた}夕方になっていた。

It had become evening without my noticing.

Example

A 「いつのまにか、^{ゆうがた}夕方になっていた」

A: It was evening before I knew it.

Notes

The phrase "itsunomanika" is used to express that something happened without you realizing it. The word "itsu" is a pronoun that means "when." The word "no" is a particle that is used to indicate possession or connection. The word "ma" is a noun that means "moment", and the

word "ni" is an adverbial particle that is used to indicate time or place.
The word "ka" is a question particle that is used to indicate a question.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a change that happened unnoticed

realizing the passage of time

expressing something noticed afterward

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverbial expression

colloquial

time expression

realization

change

Be attentive

き き
気が利く

Ki ga kiku

Be attentive

Variants

- 気が利く
be attentive
- 気が利いている
be thoughtful
- なかなか気が利いている
be well-designed

Adjusted Expression

この家のデザインは、使いやすく、よく工夫されている。

The design of this house is easy to use and well thought out.

Example

A 「この家のデザインは、使いやすく、なかなか気が利いているね」

A: The design of this house is user-friendly and well thought out.

Notes

The phrase "ki ga kiku" is used to express that something is attentive or considerate. The word "ki" is a noun that means "spirit" or "mind." The word "kiku" is a verb that means "to be effective" or "to be useful."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluating consideration or ingenuity

evaluating ease of use

expressing that something is well thought out

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

evaluative expression

consideration

ingenuity

Mention

くち
口に(する)

Kuchi ni suru

Mention

Variants

- 口にする
mention
- 一切口にしない
not mention at all
- その話を口にする
bring up the subject

Adjusted Expression

かれ かれ、その事件 じけん について一切言及 いっさいげんきゅう しなかった。

He did not refer to the incident at all.

Example

かれ かれ はその事件 じけん について一切口 いっさいくち にしなかった。

He didn't mention the incident at all.

Notes

"Kuchi ni suru" refers to mentioning or bringing up a topic, often used in negative sentences to express deliberately avoiding a subject or not saying something. It can also mean putting food or drink into one's

mouth. The word "kuchi" is a noun that means "mouth." The word "suru" is a verb that means "to do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing mention

expressing not bringing something up

expressing deliberate silence

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

mention

silence

negative sentence

Hear about

みみ
耳に(する)

Mimi ni suru

Hear about

Variants

- 耳にする
hear about
- 最近よく耳にする
hear about it often lately
- その問題を耳にする
hear that issue mentioned

Adjusted Expression

さいきん もんだい き
最近、その問題について聞くことがある。

Recently, I sometimes hear about that issue.

Example

A 「さいきん もんだい き
最近、その問題を耳にする」

A: I hear about that issue frequently these days.

Notes

The phrase "mimi ni suru" is used to express that you frequently hear about something. The word "mimi" is a noun that means "ear." The word "suru" is a verb that means "to do." This idiomatic phrase, "mimi ni suru,"

is to hear something mentioned or referred to on multiple occasions in everyday life, often indirectly or casually, through conversations, media, or public discourse.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing information one has heard

expressing hearing something as a topic

mentioning a recent topic

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

information exposure

topic

hearing expression

Obtain

て
手いに入れる

Te ni ireru

Obtain

Variants

- 手に入れる
obtain
- ようやく手に入れる
finally obtain
- 夢の家を手に入れる
get one's dream house

Adjusted Expression

かれ ながねん どりょく けっか ゆめ いえ じぶん
彼は、長年の努力の結果、ようやく夢の家を自分のものにした。

As a result of years of effort, he finally made his dream house his own.

Example

かれ ながねん どりょく すえ ゆめ いえ て い
彼は長年の努力の末、ようやく夢の家を手に入れた。

After years of hard work, he finally obtained his dream house.

Notes

"Te ni ireru" is used to express obtaining something after searching for it or making an effort to make it one's own. It is not simply about buying or receiving something.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing obtaining something through effort

expressing acquisition

sharing a sense of achievement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

acquisition

effort

achievement

Feel like

き
気がする

Ki ga suru

Feel like

Variants

- 気がする
feel like
- 見たことがある気がする
feel like I've seen it before
- そんな気がする
have a feeling

Adjusted Expression

この問題は、どこかで見たことがあるように感じる。

I feel as if I have seen this problem somewhere before.

Example

この問題、どこかで見たことがある気がする。

I feel like I've seen this problem somewhere before.

Notes

"Ki ga suru" is used when you intuitively sense or vaguely feel something, even though you are not certain about it. It carries a nuance of uncertainty, suggesting that you feel something might be true without

having concrete evidence. The word "ki" is a noun that means "spirit" or "mind." The word "suru" is a verb that means "to do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing an uncertain feeling

expressing intuitive judgment

expressing vague memory

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

sensory expression

uncertainty

intuition

Needless to say

い
言うまでもなく

Iu made mo naku

Needless to say

Variants

- 言うまでもなく
needless to say
- 言うまでもないが
it goes without saying
- 言うまでもないことだが
obviously

Adjusted Expression

どうぜん当然のことではありますが、けっかその結果は、わたし私たちにとってひじょう じゅうよう非常に重要です。

Of course, the result is extremely important for us.

Example

い言うまでもなく、けっか わたしその結果は私たちにとってひじょう じゅうよう非常に重要です。

Needless to say, the result is extremely important for us.

Notes

"Iumademonaku" is used to express that something is so obvious that it does not need to be said. The word "iu" is a verb that means "to say." The

word "mademo" is a conjunction that means "even if." The word "naku" is a negative suffix that is used to negate the verb that comes before it.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasizing obviousness

signaling shared assumption

marking omission of explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

colloquial

emphasis

presupposition

discourse marker

Countless

かぞ き
数え切れない

Kazoekirenai

Countless

Variants

- 数え切れない
countless
- 数えきれない
too many to count
- 数え切れないほど
so many that they cannot be counted

Adjusted Expression

よぞら ひじょう おお ほし かがや
夜空には、非常に多くの星が輝いています。

A very large number of stars are shining in the night sky.

Example

かぞ き ほし よぞら かがや
数え切れない星が夜空に輝いています。

Countless stars are shining in the night sky.

Notes

"Kazoekirenai" is used to express that something is so numerous that it cannot be counted. The word "kazoeru" is a verb that means "to count."

The word "kirenai" is a negative form of the verb "kiru" that means "to be able to do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a large number

hyperbolic expression of quantity

emphasizing an impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adjectival expression

colloquial

quantity expression

large number

hyperbolic expression

Timid

き ちい
気が小さい

Ki ga chiisai

Timid

Variants

- 気が小さい
timid
- 気が小さい人
a timid person
- 気が小さくて
lack courage

Adjusted Expression

(その)人は、^{しっばい}失敗を^{おそ}恐れて、^{あたら}新しいことに^{ちょうせん}挑戦しないことが多い。^{おお}

That person often avoids trying new things because they fear failure.

Example

き ちい ひと しっばい おそ ちゃ れん じ おお
気が小さい人は、失敗を恐れてチャレンジしないことが多い。

Timid people often avoid challenges because they fear failure.

Notes

"Ki ga chiisai" is used to express that someone is timid or lacks courage. The word "ki" is a noun that means "spirit" or "mind." The word "chiisai" is an i-adjective that means "small."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing timidity

evaluating lack of courage

describing a person's character

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

character evaluation

personality description

timidity

Capture one's heart

こころ うば
心を奪う

Kokoro wo ubau

Capture one's heart

Variants

- 心を奪う
capture one's heart
- 心を奪われる
be captivated
- 聴く人の心を奪う
capture the hearts of those who listen

Adjusted Expression

かのじょ うた き ひと ふか かんどう
彼女の歌は、聴く人を深く感動させる。

Her singing deeply moves those who listen.

Example

かのじょ うた き ひと こころ うば
彼女の歌は、聴く人の心を奪う。

Her singing captures the hearts of those who listen.

Notes

"Kokoro wo ubau" is used to express that something captivates or deeply moves someone's heart. The word "kokoro" is a noun that means "heart"

or "mind." The word "ubau" is a verb that means "to snatch" or "to capture."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing strong charm

expressing deep emotion

describing the power to move someone's heart

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

emotional expression

captivation

deep emotion

Hurry

いそ
急ぐ

Isogu

Hurry

Variants

- 急ぐ
hurry
- 急いで
hurry up
- 急いで！
be in a hurry

Adjusted Expression

おく 遅れないように、はや 早く こうどう 行動してください。

Please act quickly so that you will not be late.

Example

いそ 急いで！おく 遅れるよ。

Hurry up! You'll be late.

Notes

"Isogu" is used to express that you are in a hurry or rushing to do something. The word "isogu" is a verb that means "to hurry" or "to rush."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing hurry

urging someone to act quickly

warning about being late

Tags EN

immediate grammar

verb

colloquial

urging

time expression

warning

Smile gently

め ほそ
目を細める

Me wo hosomeru

Smile gently

Variants

- 目を細める
smile gently
- 優しく目を細める
smile warmly
- 目を細めて喜ぶ
narrow one's eyes with joy

Adjusted Expression

かのじょ まご せいちょう よろこ やさ ほほえ
彼女は、孫の成長を喜び、優しく微笑んだ。

She was pleased with her grandchild's growth and smiled gently.

Example

かのじょ まご せいちょう よろこ やさ め ほそ
彼女は孫の成長を喜んで、優しく目を細めた。

She smiled warmly as she watched her grandchild grow.

Notes

"Me wo hosomeru" is used to express that one smiles gently or warmly while watching something or someone. The word "me" is a noun that means "eye." The word "hosomeru" is a verb that means "to narrow."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing warm feeling describing a joyful facial expression

expressing the feeling of watching over someone

Tags EN

immediate grammar idiomatic expression body expression emotional expression joy

facial expression

Offer help

て
手を差し伸べる

Te wo sashinoberu

Offer help

Variants

- 手を差し伸べる
offer help
- 困っている人に手を差し伸べる
lend a helping hand
- 救いの手を差し伸べる
extend a helping hand

Adjusted Expression

かれは、^{こま}困っている人を見ると、^{たす}助けようとする。

When he sees someone in need, he tries to help them.

Example

かれは、^{こま}困っている人を見ると、^て手を差し伸べる。

He offers help to people in need when he sees them.

Notes

"Te wo sashinoberu" is used to express that you offer help or support to someone in need. The word "te" is a noun that means "hand." The word "sashinoberu" is a verb that means "to stretch out."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing help

supporting someone in need

describing a kind action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

body expression

help

support

kindness

Cut corners

てぬ
手を抜く

Te wo nuku

Cut corners

Variants

- 手を抜く
cut corners
- 手を抜いた仕事
do careless work
- 仕事で手を抜く
do a sloppy job

Adjusted Expression

びるけんせつ ひつよう さぎょう じゅうぶん おこな けっか だいじこ おこ
ビル建設で、必要な作業を十分に行わなかった結果、大事故が起きた。

A major accident occurred in the building construction because the necessary work was not done properly.

Example

びるけんせつ てぬ しごと けっか だいじこ おこ
ビル建設で、手を抜いた仕事をした結果、大事故が起きた。

A major accident occurred in the construction of the building as a result of the work done carelessly.

Notes

The phrase "te wo nuku" means to do something carelessly or to cut corners. The word "te" is a noun that means "hand." The word "nuku" is a verb that means "to pull out."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing inadequate work pointing out omission or negligence

explaining the cause of an accident or failure

Tags EN

immediate grammar idiomatic expression body expression work situation

negligence failure

Lose enthusiasm

ねつ
熱が冷める

Netsu ga sameru

Lose enthusiasm

Variants

- 熱が冷める
lose enthusiasm
- すぐに熱が冷める
cool off quickly
- 熱が冷めてしまった
lose interest

Adjusted Expression

あたら しゅみ きょうみ うしな
新しい趣味への興味を、すぐに失ってしまった。

I quickly lost interest in my new hobby.

Example

あたら しゅみ むちゅう ねつ さ
新しい趣味に夢中だったが、すぐに熱が冷めてしまった。

I was really into my new hobby, but my enthusiasm cooled off quickly.

Notes

The phrase "netsu ga sameru" means to lose enthusiasm. It is used when you lose interest in a hobby or work. Of course, it can be used when you really lose enthusiasm, but it is often used when you lose interest. When

you catch a cold and have a fever, you say "netsu ga sagaru" or "netsu wa mou nai."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing loss of interest

expressing a decline in enthusiasm

describing a change in feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

body expression

emotional expression

interest

enthusiasm

Read the room

くうき よ
空気を読む

Kuuki wo yomu

Read the room

Variants

- 空気を読む
read the room
- 空気を読んで
read the situation
- 空気が読めない
can't read the room

Adjusted Expression

じょうきょう しゅうい ふん いき はあく てきせつ こうどう
状 況や周囲の雰囲気^{はあく}を把握して、適切^{てきせつ}に行動^{こうどう}してください。

Understand the situation and the surrounding atmosphere, and act appropriately.

Example

A 「^{いま}今、^{はなし}話を^{つづ}続けても大丈夫かな？」 B 「^{くうき}空気を^よ読んで」

A: Is it okay to continue the conversation now? B: Read the room.

Notes

The phrase "kuuki wo yomu" is used to express that you are aware of the atmosphere or mood of a situation and act accordingly. The word "kuuki"

is a noun that means "air" or "atmosphere." The word "yomu" is a verb that means "to read."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing reading the atmosphere

urging behavior appropriate to the situation

expressing interpersonal consideration

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

interpersonal relations

atmosphere

consideration

Sharp pain

いた はし
痛みが走る

Itami ga hashiru

Sharp pain

Variants

- 痛みが走る
feel a sharp pain
- 歯に痛みが走る
a sharp pain runs through
- 鋭い痛みが走る
sharp pain

Adjusted Expression

は するど いた かん
歯に鋭い痛みを感じた。

I felt a sharp pain in my tooth.

Example

は いた はし
歯に痛みが走った。

I felt a sharp pain in my tooth.

Notes

The phrase "itami ga hashiru" is used to express that you feel a sharp pain in a specific part of your body. The word "itami" is a noun that means "pain." The word "hashiru" is a verb that means "to run."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing sharp pain

describing a bodily sensation

expressing sudden pain

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

body expression

pain

sensory expression

Sleepiness

ねむけ
眠気

Nemuke

Sleepiness

Variants

- 眠気
sleepiness
- 眠気が来た
feel sleepy
- 眠気を感じる
drowsiness comes over me

Adjusted Expression

ひる はん た ねむ
昼ご飯を食べたあと、眠くなった。

I became sleepy after eating lunch.

Example

ひる はん た ねむ け き
昼ご飯を食べたあと、眠気が来た。

I felt sleepy after eating lunch.

Notes

The word "nemuke" is used to express that you are sleepy or drowsy. The word "nemuke" is a noun that means "sleepiness."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing sleepiness

describing a bodily sensation

expressing a post-meal state

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

body expression

sensory expression

sleepiness

Be excited

こころ おど
心が躍る

Kokoro ga odoru

Be excited

Variants

- 心が躍る
be excited
- 心が躍った
feel thrilled
- わくわくして心が躍る
one's heart dances

Adjusted Expression

かれ あたら しごと きたい
彼は、新しい仕事に期待して、わくわくしていた。

He was excited and looking forward to his new job.

Example

かれ あたら しごと こころ おど
彼は、新しい仕事に、心が躍った。

He was excited about his new job.

Notes

The phrase "kokoro ga odoru" is used to express that you are excited or thrilled about something. The word "kokoro" is a noun that means

"heart" or "mind." The word "odoru" is a verb that means "to dance" or "to jump."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing anticipation or excitement

describing a thrilled feeling

reacting to something new

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

body expression

emotional expression

anticipation

excitement

At the edge of a cliff

がけ
崖っぷち

Gakeppuchi

At the edge of a cliff

Variants

- 崖っぷち
at the edge of a cliff
- 崖っぷちに立たされている
be on the brink
- 仕事で崖っぷち
be in a desperate situation

Adjusted Expression

かれは、仕事で非常に困難な状況に追い込まれている。

He has been driven into a very difficult situation at work.

Example

もうこれ以上、時間もお金もかけられない状況に追い込まれて、彼は、仕事で崖っぷちに立たされている。

He has been driven into a situation where he can't spend any more time or money, and he is on the brink at work.

Notes

The phrase "gakeppuchi" is used to express that you are in a difficult situation where you have no choice but to take action. The word "gake" is a noun that means "cliff." The word "ppuchi" is a noun that means "edge."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing being cornered

describing a critical situation

expressing having few options left

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

crisis

difficulty

work situation

Get through

の 乗り切る

Norikiru

Get through

Variants

- 乗り切る
get through
- 何とか乗り切る
manage to get through
- 大変な仕事を乗り切る
get through a tough job

Adjusted Expression

たいへん しごと 大変な仕事だったが、なん さいご 最後まで終わることができた。

It was a tough job, but I managed to complete it to the end.

Example

たいへん しごと 大変な仕事だったけど、なん の き 何とか乗り切った。

It was a tough job, but I managed to get through it.

Notes

The phrase "nori kiru" is used to express that you have successfully completed a difficult task or situation. The word "nori" is a noun that

means "ride" or "get on." The word "kiru" is a verb that means "to cut" or "to get through."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing getting through difficulty

reporting completion

sharing a sense of achievement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

verb

colloquial

difficulty

achievement

work situation

Be surprised

びっくりした

Bikkuri shita

Be surprised

Variants

- びっくりした
be surprised
- うわっ、びっくりした
that scared me
- 心臓止まるかと思った
I thought my heart would stop

Adjusted Expression

とつぜん できごと おどろ
突然の出来事に、とても驚いた。

I was very surprised by the sudden event.

Example

うわっ、びっくりした！心臓止まるかと思った。

Wow, that scared me! I thought my heart would stop.

Notes

The phrase "bikkuri shita" is used to express that you are surprised or startled by something. The word "bikkuri" is a noun that means "surprise" or "shock." The word "shita" is the past tense of the verb "suru," which means "to do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing surprise

reacting to a sudden event

sharing strong surprise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

surprise

reaction expression

That's tough

それはたいへん

Sore wa taihen

That's tough

Variants

- それはたいへん
That's tough
- それは大変
That must have been hard
- それは大変だったね
That sounds rough

Adjusted Expression

それは、とても^{たいへん}大変なことだった^{おも}と思います。

I think that must have been very difficult.

Example

A 「昨日、^{きのう}徹夜^{てつや}で仕事^{しごと}を終わ^おらせた」 B 「それはたいへん」

A: I stayed up all night to finish my work yesterday. B: That's tough.

Notes

The phrase "sore wa taihen" is used to express sympathy or understanding when someone tells you about a difficult or challenging situation. The word "sore" is a pronoun that means "that." The word "wa"

is a particle that is used to indicate the topic of a sentence. The word "taihen" is a noun that means "tough" or "difficult."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing sympathy

reacting to someone's difficulty

sharing understanding or empathy

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

empathy

sympathy

Let's do more

もっとやろう

Motto yarou

Let's do more

Variants

- もっとやろう
let's do more
- もう少しやろう
let's do a little more
- もっと続けよう
let's keep going

Adjusted Expression

まだ時間じかんがあるので、もう少しすこ続けつづましょう。

Since we still have time, let's continue a little longer.

Example

まだ時間じかんがあるから、もっとやろう。

We still have time, so let's keep going.

Notes

The phrase "motto yarou" is used to encourage someone to do more or to keep going. The word "motto" is an adverb that means "more." The word "yarou" is a verb that means "to do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouraging continuation

suggesting doing more

positive urging

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

invitation

urging

continuation

Like

き い
気に入る

Ki ni iru

Like

Variants

- 気に入る
like
- 気に入っている
be pleased with
- 今日の服、気に入っている
like today's outfit

Adjusted Expression

きょう ふく、じぶん この あ
今日の服が、自分の好みに合っている。

Today's outfit suits my taste.

Example

きょう ふく き い
今日の服、気に入っている。

I like today's outfit.

Notes

"Ki ni iru" is used to express that you like something or that something catches your eye. The word "ki" is a noun that means "spirit" or "mind." The word "iru" is a verb that means "to be."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that something suits one's taste

expressing satisfaction

evaluating an object

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

preference

evaluative expression

satisfaction

Right now

いま
今すぐ

Ima sugu

Right now

Variants

- 今すぐ
right now
- 今すぐ行く
go right now
- 今すぐ行かないと
if we don't go right now

Adjusted Expression

おく
遅れないように、ただちに行く必要がある。
いま い ひつよう

We need to go immediately so that we will not be late.

Example

いま い おく
今すぐ行かないと遅れるよ。

We'll be late if we don't leave right now.

Notes

"Ima sugu" is used to express that you need to do something immediately or right away. The word "ima" is a noun that means "now." The word "sugu" is an adverb that means "immediately" or "right away."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

urging immediate action

expressing time pressure

warning about being late

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverbial expression

colloquial

time expression

urging

urgency

Put in an extra effort

ひとてま
一手間かける

Hitotema kakeru

Put in an extra effort

Variants

- 一手間かける
put in an extra effort
- 料理に一手間かける
add an extra step
- 一手間加える
make one extra effort

Adjusted Expression

りょうり ひと くふう くわ あじ おお よ
料理に、もう一つ工夫を加えると、味が大きく良くなる。

If you add one more touch to the dish, the taste improves greatly.

Example

りょうり ひとてま あじ よ
料理に一手間かけると、味が(ぐっと)良くなる。

Putting in an extra effort in cooking makes the taste much better.

Notes

"Hitotema kakeru" is used to express that you put in an extra effort or take an extra step to improve something. The word "hitotema" is a noun

that means "extra effort" or "extra step." The word "kakeru" is a verb that means "to put in" or "to spend."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing adding ingenuity

extra work for improvement

evaluating careful work

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

ingenuity

cooking

improvement

Cheers

かんぱい
乾杯

Kanpai

Cheers

Variants

- 乾杯
cheers
- 乾杯！
toast
- みんなで乾杯
let's make a toast

Adjusted Expression

飲^のむ前^{まえ}に、みんなで祝^{いわ}うための挨拶^{あいさつ}をする。

Before drinking, everyone makes a toast to celebrate.

Example

かんぱい
乾杯！

Cheers!

Notes

"Kanpai" is used to express a toast or to say cheers before drinking. The word "kanpai" is a noun that means "toast" or "cheers." The literal translation of "kanpai" is "dry cup."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

toast before drinking

greeting before drinking

expression for sharing the occasion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

greeting expression

colloquial

drinking situation

Colophon

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